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An Ayurvedic Management of Hypertension - A Single Case Study

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ABSTRACT

Hypertension is one of the leading cause of global burden of disease. Hypertension doubles the risk of cardiovascular diseases, including coronary heart disease, congestive heart failure, ischemic and haemorrhagic stroke, renal failure and peripheral arterial disease. In industrialized societies, blood pressure increases steadily during the first two decades of life. Approximately 13-15% of total deaths and 92 million disability adjusted life years worldwide were attributable to high blood pressure in 2001.¹ In *Ayurveda* there is no mentioning of any disease which can be directly correlated with the hypertension, but based on the its presentation we can correlate hypertension with *Raktagata Vata*. Though there are a number of anti-hypertensive medicine available, but in this era of health consciousness there is demand for herbal or herbomineral formulations which can be safely used in the management of hypertension. To analyse the effect *Ayurvedic* management of hypertension with *Kamadudha Rasa*, *Amalaki Rasayan* and *Erand Bhrusht Haritaki* in the effective management of Primary (essential) hypertension. This was a single case study. In this study a diagnosed patient of essential hypertension was taken. There was significant improvement in the clinical sign and symptoms.

Keywords: Hypertension, *Raktagata Vata*, *Ucharaktachapa*, *Kamadudha Rasa*, *Amalaki Rasayan*, *Erand Bhrusht Haritaki*

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INTRODUCTION

Blood pressure is defined as the force exerted by the blood against any unit area of the vessel wall, while hypertension is a condition in which the blood vessels have persistently raised pressure. Systemic hypertension in adults is defined clinically as persistent elevation of SBP (Systolic blood pressure) of > 130 mm of Hg or DBP (Diastolic blood pressure) of > 80 mm of Hg. Hypertension can be categorized as primary/essential or idiopathic with no definable cause while in secondary hypertension there may be some factors which contribute to its pathogenesis. In more than 95% of cases, specific underlying cause of hypertension cannot be found. Hypertension is predominantly an asymptomatic condition and the diagnosis is usually made during routine examination or when a complication arises.² In *Ayurveda* there is no mentioning of any disease which can be directly correlated with the hypertension. But based on its presentation some scholars correlate hypertension with *Raktagata Vata*. There is no separate description of *Raktagata Vata* in *Ayurvedic* literature with special reference to hypertension or *Ucharaktachapa*. In *Raktagata Vata* vitiated *Vata* especially *Vyan Vayu* (Type of *Vayu*) gets accumulated in *Rakta* (Blood) which then vitiate *Pitta* which is related to *Rakta* as *Ashraya Ashrayi Bahava*.³ Some scholars put hypertension as *Rasaj Vikara* as *Hridaya* (Heart) is the *Moola* of *Rasavaha Srotas* and *Dash Dhamanis*⁴ and hypertension is related to the *Hridaya* and *Dhamanis* (Blood Vessels). *Acharaya Vagbhatta* while explaining the *Karma* of Vitiated *Vata* mentioned about *Sankocha* (Constriction), *Spandana* (Palpitation)⁵ which can be involved in the *Samprapti* (Pathogenesis) of hypertension. When there is *Spandana* due to vitiated *Vata* this leads to increased heart rate and resultant increased cardiac output and development of hypertension. *Sankocha* (Constriction) leads to vasoconstriction which causes increased peripheral resistance and result in increased blood pressure.

Case Study

46 years old married, male came into OPD on 16/02/2026 with history of essential hypertension was taking angiotensin II receptor blocker (ARB) since three months.

History

As per the history given by the patient, he was absolutely fit before three months and gradually developed intermittent symptoms of headache or heaviness, restlessness for which he consulted to an allopathic physician and was investigated. After investigation he was diagnosed as case of essential hypertension and doctor advised him a ARB. According to patient he did not find much relief and decided for *Ayurvedic* management and came in the OPD on 16/02/2026. His blood pressure was 158/86 mm of Hg with pulse rate 82/min at time of examination. There was no

history of any comorbidity with no family history. Patient was still on medication but patient's blood pressure was on higher side with persistence of above said complaints. Patient was examined thoroughly with *Darshan* (Inspection), *Sparshan* (Palpation) and *Prashan* (History taking) *Pariksha* and was found that he was having constipation with intermittent flatulence and indigestion. His *Prakriti* (Bodily constitution) was *Vataj Kaphaja*.

Clinical Examination:

Physical Examination

Blood pressure

Table 1: Blood Pressure Readings Before Treatment

	Right Arm			Left Arm		
Supine Posture	Sitting Posture	Standing Posture	Supine Posture	Sitting Posture	Standing Posture	
158/86 mm of Hg	156/86 mm of Hg	156/86 mm of Hg	158/86 mm of Hg	156/86 mm of Hg	156/86 mm of Hg	

Patient's blood pressure was checked after rest for 5 minutes, both arm BP was checked. Blood pressure was checked in supine, sitting and standing positions to rule out any postural variation in blood pressure.

- Pulse rate – 82/min.
- Respiratory rate – 17/min.
- Temperature – 98.0⁰ F
- Edema – Absent
- Pallor – Absent
- Icterus – Absent
- Clubbing – Absent

Ashtasthana Pariksha

- *Nadi* (Pulse) – *Vataj Kaphaja*
- *Mootra* (Urine) - 4-5 times per day
- *Malam* (Fecal matter) - Constipation
- *Jihwa* (Tongue) - *Nirama*
- *Sabdham* (Voice of patient) – Normal speech
- *Sparsham* (Tactilation) - *Samshitoshna*
- *Druk* (Eyes and Vision) - *Prakruta*
- *Akriti* (General body build) – *Madhyama*

Systemic Examination: Systemic examination did not depicted any significant changes.

Laboratory Investigation:

Laboratory investigations done on 12/01/2026

Table 2: Hematological Investigations

S.No	Name of Investigation	Findings
1.	Lipid Profile	
	Cholesterol	191 mg/dl
	Triglycerides	124 mg/dl
	HDL	52.4 mg/dl
	LDL	106.46 mg/dl
	VLDL	30 mg/dl
2.	Serum Urea	23.24 mg/dl
3.	Serum Creatinine	0.83 mg/dl

Treatment Regimen:

The treatment was carried out with the following medicines with dietary precautions for 21 days with follow up after every 7 days.

Table 3: Treatment Regimen (Internal Medication)

S.No.	Name of Formulation	Dosages	Ingredients	Reference
1	<i>Kamadudha Rasa</i>	250 mg BD	<i>Mukta</i> (Pearl), <i>Pravala</i> (Coral), <i>Shukti</i> (Pearl oyster), <i>Sankha</i> (Conch shell), <i>Varatika</i> , (Marine shell) <i>Swarna Garika</i> (Red ochre), <i>Guduchi</i> (<i>Tinospora cardifolia</i>)	<i>Ras Tantra Sara & Sidha Prayoga Sangrah</i> ⁶
2	<i>Amalaki Rasayan</i>	2 gm BD	<i>Amalaki</i> (<i>Emblica officinalis</i>)	<i>Bhav Prakash Nighantu, Haritakyadi Varga</i> ⁷
3	<i>Erand Bhrusht Haritaki</i>	2 tab. HS	<i>Bal Haritaki</i> (<i>Terminalia chebula</i>), <i>Erand Oil</i> (<i>Ricinus communis</i>)	<i>Bharat Bhaishyaja Ratnakar</i> ⁸

OBSERVATION AND RESULT:**Table 4: Blood Pressure Readings**

RIGHT ARM				LEFT ARM				
Position	Before treatment	After 1 st week	After 2 nd week	After 3 rd week	Before treatment	After 1 st week	After 2 nd week	After 3 rd week
Supine Posture	158/86 mm of Hg	130/82 mm of Hg	130/80 mm of Hg	124/80 mm of Hg	158/86 mm of Hg	130/82 mm of Hg	130/80 mm of Hg	124/80 mm of Hg
Sitting Posture	156/86 mm of Hg	128/82 mm of Hg	128/80 mm of Hg	122/80 mm of Hg	156/86 mm of Hg	128/82 mm of Hg	128/80 mm of Hg	122/80 mm of Hg
Supine Posture	156/86 mm of Hg	128/82 mm of Hg	128/80 mm of Hg	122/80 mm of Hg	156/86 mm of Hg	128/82 mm of Hg	128/80 mm of Hg	122/80 mm of Hg
Pulse Rate	82/min	74/min	76/min	70/min	82/min	74/min	76/min	70/min

Table 5: Results Related to Symptomatology

S.No.	Symptom/Sign	Before treatment	After 1 st week	After 2 nd week	After 3 rd week
1.	Headache/Heaviness	Present	Intermittent	Occasional	Absent
2.	Restlessness	Present	Absent	Absent	Absent
3.	Constipation	Present	Intermittent	Absent	Absent

This regimen was advised twice in a day with water and was instructed to avoid extra salt, tea, coffee, spicy, fried and heavy food. Patient was advised for walk in the morning and evening. Initially ARB which the patient was taking continued along with above regimen. After the first week of treatment that allopathic medicine was stopped after tapering down the dosage. After 2nd week there was significant improvement and in the 3rd week he was feeling completely healthy and his blood pressure was in normal range. Above said regimen was continued for 2 months and patient got relief.

DISCUSSION:

In this case the actual cause of high blood pressure was vitiated *Apana Vayu* and vitiated *Pitta Dosha*. This Vitiating *Apana Vayu* (Type of *Vayu*) moves in *Pratiloma Gati* (Abnormal Movement) and produces *Apanaavruta Vyana* (Obstructed movement of *Vyana*) and then does the *Rakta Dushti* and in turn result in vitiation of *Pitta* which is related to *Rakta* as *Ashraya Ashrayi Bahava*. *Vata* which is the most important *Dosha* in the body and is the moving force behind the *Kapha* and *Pitta*. In this pathogenesis the path of *Vyana Vayu* was obstructed (*Avarana*) which is responsible for the circulation of *Rakta* in the *Raktavaha Srotas* (Blood vessels) as a result *Rakta Dhātu* movement also gets hampered which leads to the development of hypertension and secondly seat of *Vyana Vayu* is *Hridaya*⁹ as mentioned by *Acharaya Vagbhata*, so if there is vitiation in the *Vyan Vayu*, as a consequence functioning of *Hridaya* will also get disturbed which can be the cause of hypertension and palpitation.

Probable mode of action of *Kamdudha Rasa*

Mukta Panchamrita is one of the important *Sudakalpa* and most of the ingredients of this *Kalpa* are *Pitta* and *Vata Shamaka*. It is specifically used in *Pittaj Vikaras*. Its ingredients have *Deepan Pachan* properties. It also acts as a *Rasayana* and tonic for *Hridaya*. *Mukta* and *Pravala Bhasma* have *Madura Rasa*, *Sheeta Virya* and *Madhura Vipaka* while *Sankha Bhasma*, *Varatika Bhasma* & *Guduchi Satva* is having *Tikta/Katu Rasa* and because of these properties it pacifies *Pitta*. *Kshariya guna* of *Shankha* and *Shukti Bhasma* neutralize *Amltava* of *Vidagdha* (Vitiating) *Pitta*.

Probable mode of action of *Amalaki Rasayan*;

In *Amalaki Rasayan*; *Amala Rasa* of *Amalaki* pacifies *Vata* and *Madhura* and *Sheeta Guna* balances *Pitta* and also acts as *Rasayana* and rejuvenates the body and is also a good remedy for constipation. It is indicated in *Aruchi*, *Agnimandhya*, *Ajirna* in *Ayurvedic* formulary of India.¹⁰

Probable mode of action of *Erand Bhrusht Haritaki*

In a whole this entire combination of formulations help to pacify the vitiated *Pitta* and *Anulomana* of *Vayu* and detoxify the effect of vitiated *Pitta*, and by this *Samprapti* (Pathogenesis) *Vighatana* of hypertension was done.

CONCLUSION:

There is no *Vyadhi* in *Ayurveda* classics which can be directly correlated with hypertension. So on the basis of the sign and symptoms we can name it as *Raktagata Vata* in which there is vitiation of *Vata & Pitta*. In this patient the *Samprapti* ends in *Apanavruta Vyana* results in *Sankocha* of blood vessels result in raised blood pressure and *Spandana* leads to palpitation and *Apanavruta Prana* leads to frontal headache along with heaviness. Vitiated *Vata* further results in the vitiation of *Raktadhatu* and thus the *Pitta* because of *Ashraya Ashrayi Bahava*. In this study the entire regimen was planned according to *Dosha* predominance and to target the *Samprapti Vighatana*. This study highlights the efficiency of above mentioned *Ayurvedic* herbo-mineral formulation in the effective management of hypertension. In *Ayurvedic* management of any *Vyadhi* it is of prime importance to analyse the *Samprapti* of that particular *Vyadhi* which can be different in different individuals and further by understanding the *Samprapti Vighatana Chikitsa* has to be adopted based on *Avastha* of *Dosha* vitiation.

REFERENCES:

1. Anthony S. Fauci et al., Harrison's Principles of Internal Medicine, Volume 2, 19th edition, Chapter 298, McGraw-Hill Companies, United States, 2015, 1611p.
2. Brian R. Walker et al., Davidson's Principles and Practice of Medicine, 22nd edition, Chapter 18, Churchill Livingstone Elsevier, China, 2014, p. 607-608.
3. Brahmanand Tripathi, Astanga Hridayam of Srimadvagbhata, Nirmala Hindi Commentary, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Pratishthan, New Delhi, Sutra Sthana, Verse 11/26, 2009, p. 165.
4. Harish Chandra Singh Kushwaha, Charak Samhita of Acharya Charak, Ayurved Dipika Hindi commentary, 1st part, Chaukhambha Orientalia, Varanasi, Vimana Sthana, 05/8, 2016, p. 631.
5. Brahmanand Tripathi, Astanga Hridayam of Srimadvagbhata, Nirmala Hindi Commentary, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Pratishthan, New Delhi, Sutra Sthana, Verse 12/49-50, 2015, p. 178.

6. Ras Tantra Sara & Sidha Prayoga Sangrah, Krishana Gopal Ayurveda Bhawan, Ajmer, Kalera, 2006, p.444.
7. Vishvanath Dwivadi, Bhavprakash Nighantu, Motilal Banarasi Das, Delhi, Haritakyadi Varga, Verse 39-40, 2007, p. 9.
8. Bharat Bhaishyajya Ratnakar by NC Shah, 1ST ed., Vol I-Vol V. B. Jain Publishers, New Delhi, 2005, p.193.
9. Brahmanand Tripathi, Astanga Hridayam of Srimadvagbhata, Nirmala Hindi Commentary, Chaukhamba Sanskrit Pratishthan, New Delhi, Sutra Sthana, 12/7, 2019, p. 171.
10. The Ayurvedic formulary of India, Part 1, Second Edition, The Controller of publications, Civil Lines, Delhi, 2003, p. 106.

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